

Peruse This Paper to Cognize Point Rating Method in Job Evaluation Using an Hypothetical General Printers' Company Limited

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Abstract: Job evaluation is a process through which private and public organizations can make decisions over relative worth of jobs. Effective job evaluation undertaking depends on analytical approaches and methods such as the point rating. It can be very cumbersome to choose the compensable factors and assign points correctly during point rating because of lacking of skills and information among job evaluators. The objective of this paper was to apply the point rating method of job evaluation to evaluate the job clusters at a hypothetical General Printers' Company Limited. Based on a review of literature, the paper practiced all nine steps that it anticipates were used by Job Evaluation Committee to rate points to the jobs particularly in the Trades Skilled job cluster at the Company. The paper maximizes skills and sharing of information on point rating method among Company owners, managers, employee, interns and trade unions representatives being potential participants in the job evaluation Committees. The difficulties encountered in establishing points for jobs among the target audience will be solved and subsequently, their capacity to participate in job evaluation Committees increased due to knowledge and skills gained from a perusal of this paper.

Keywords: Point rating, Trades Skilled Jobs, worth.

1. INTRODUCTION

Job evaluation is a vital function in Human Resource Management and leads to fair and equitable compensation decisions (Lamont, 1995). It involves an assessment of the relative worth of jobs which helps in assigning the pay rates based on the value of each job in institutions with a variety of jobs (ICN, 2010). The effective undertaking of job evaluation depends on several approaches and methods (Masanja, 2019). One of such approaches is the analytical approach in which the point rating method has become one among dominant techniques like the Factor-Comparison method (Armstrong et al., 2005). The point rating method (point-factor method) belongs to the analytical approach because it involves a process of analyzing compensable job factors which help in the formulation of the hierarchy of jobs depending on the value of each in the organization; unlike the non-analytical job evaluation schemes which compare the whole jobs in terms of their compensable factors without their depth analysis in establishing grades or rank of the job value (EOC, 2009).

Regarding the point rating method in job evaluation, it identifies compensable factors for a cluster (family) of jobs and places points on each factor (Kareem & Oke, 2011). This action leads to the summation of point scores in which the highest scored points determine the highest valuable job in the organization (Sukwadi & Gerald, 2010). Pandey and Leelashree (2012) defined point rating system as “an analytical method which breaks down each job into several factors; for example, skill, responsibility, and effort, with these factors sometimes being further broken down into sub-factors like

education, decision making and dexterity. These sub-factors will be further divided into degrees or levels. Points are awarded for each factor according to a predetermined scale and the total points decide a job's place in the ranking order”.

Even though the point rating method has been useful in awarding points to job factors based on a predetermined scale, the method is too bureaucratic and consumes much time during its utilization as suggested by Bhavika (2019). The method procedures which require Job Evaluation Committee to develop points for rating jobs are complex while many personnel who are supposed to participate in job evaluation using this method lack skills, experience, and information on its application (Acas, 2014; Bergmann & Scarpello, 2001; Suff & Reilly, 2006). In this regard, the paper's objective was to apply the point rating method to evaluate jobs at a hypothetical General Printers' Company Limited based on procedures that would have been used by the Job Evaluation Committee. The motivation for writing this paper was to maximize skills and sharing information about the point rating method. The paper would benefit Company owners, managers, employees, interns and trade unions representatives by acquiring skills and information on operationalization of the point rating method.

2. STEPS FOR IMPLEMENTING POINT RATING METHOD IN JOB EVALUATION

The extant works of literature explain at least nine steps expressed as necessary in conducting the point rating method during job evaluation (Bergmann & Scarpello, 2001; Prentice Hall, 2008). Before following all the steps in the point rating method of job evaluation, the top management normally appoints the Job Evaluation Committee (JEC) to evaluate the jobs using the point rating method (Ontario Tech, 2021). However, it should be understood that the JEC appointment does not only take place during the point rating method used but also happens with other techniques such as the Factor-Comparison Method and the non-analytical techniques including job ranking method and classification or job grading (ERI, 2021). The JEC would consist of at least 4 to 9 representatives from management and union while an external facilitator may join to provide technical advice to the activities of the Committee (Algonquin College, 2017). The Committee tries as much as possible to grasp the nature of jobs and conduct positions' evaluation impartially and objectively (University of Otago, n.d.).

After the appointment of JEC, its members enter **STEP 1** in which they identify a cluster of jobs for evaluation (Armstrong, 2005). A cluster of jobs include a group of jobs with similar characteristics like those requiring the similar knowledge and skill set (Kumar, 2010). A firm can have various clusters of job such as the Management jobs which may be comprised of the President, Manager, Supervisor and Coach. Another job cluster in a firm can include Education and teaching jobs comprising of Early Childhood educator, teacher, Tutor, Assistant Lecturer, Lecturer, and Professor. Other clusters of job may include the Skilled Agricultural, Forestry, and Fishery jobs, Crafts and Related Trades, Technician and Associated Professional jobs, Clerical Jobs, Services and Sales jobs (ILO, 2012). All these clusters can have their points rated to various compensable factors to establish the most worthy job. Figure 1 below displays the procedural steps of the point rating technique including the first step which has been clarified in this paragraph.

Figure 1: Steps in Point Rating Method of Job Evaluation

Key

CFS = Compensable Factors

Source: Adapted from Bergmann & Scarpello (2001)

Key: CFS = Compensable Factors, APVFD = Assign Point Values to Factors' Degrees

JEPM = Job Evaluation Point Manual Preparation

After identifying the clusters of jobs in step one, the JEC enters **STEP 2** which becomes a very important procedure in which the JEC conducts job analysis by describing and specifying the job positions considered under point rating job evaluation (Bergmann & Scarpello, 2001). Job analysis describes the nature of job content in terms of duties, responsibility, tasks, reporting relationship, performance standards, and specification which contains information regarding qualifications and experience (Anderson & Caldwell, 2018). Job analysis should be conducted to provide clues of factors to be considered during the rating of points on the worth of jobs in the evaluation process (Suff & Reilly, 2006).

STEP 3 follows job analysis conducted in step two and requires JEC to make a selection of compensable factors (CFs) to use in evaluating the jobs. Several compensable factors can be selected by the JEC and may range from Effort, Responsibility, Decision Making, Skills and Education, Working Conditions, Freedom to Act, Supervision, Job Difficulty, Accountability, Contacts, and so forth (Lamont, 1995). JEC may further break the compensable factors into sub-factors but a simplified list of factors helps the Committee to reach reliable results than a complicated point rating system (Lawshe Jr. & Wilson, 1947). Previous JEC tended to use at least 3 to 5 major compensable factors which are capable to increase the probability of having accurate results than selecting so many compensable factors (Grant, 1951).

Step 3 normally is followed by **STEP 4** in which the JEC defines the Compensable Factors selected for use (Bergmann & Scarpello, 2001). All factors that are chosen would be defined clearly and in specific terms to reflect their meaning based on the job cluster under job evaluation (Ehrenberg & Smith, 1987). The major factors and sub-factors if used will be defined so that they are understood by JEC members in advance. Let's assume that JEC is defining three compensable factors which include Communication and relationship skills, Knowledge, training, and experience as well as the Analytical and judgment skills. Definitions of such compensable factors may read as shown in Table 1 below

Table 1: A Sample of Compensable Factors Definitions

Compensable Factors	Definition Derived by Job Evaluation Committee
Communication and relationship Skills	This factor measures the skills required to communicate, establish and maintain relationships and gain the cooperation of others. It takes account of the skills required to motivate, negotiate, persuade, make presentations, train others, empathize, communicate unpleasant news sensitively and provide counseling and reassurance. It also takes account of difficulties involved in exercising these skills.
Knowledge, Training, and Experience	This factor measures all the forms of knowledge required to fulfill the job responsibilities satisfactorily. This includes theoretical and practical knowledge; professional, specialist, or technical knowledge; and knowledge of the policies, practices, and procedures associated with the job. It takes account of the educational level normally expected as well as the equivalent level of knowledge gained without undertaking a formal course of study; and the practical experience required to fulfill the job responsibilities satisfactorily.
Analytical and Judgment Skills	This factor measures the analytical and judgmental skills required to fulfill the job responsibilities satisfactorily. It takes account of requirements for analytical skills to diagnose a problem or illness and understand complex situations or information, and judgmental skills to formulate solutions and recommend/decide

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Compensable Factors	Definition Derived by Job Evaluation Committee
	on the best course of action/treatment.
Note other compensable factors: Planning and Organizing Skills, Physical Skills, Financial and Physical Resources Responsibilities, Policy and Service Development Implementation, Human Resources Responsibilities, Research and Development Responsibility, Mental Effort, Physical Effort, and Stress, Working Conditions, Autonomy, Complexity of Work, Judgment, Supervision Exercised, Financial and Material Accountability, Responsibility for Health and Safety of others, Physical Working Conditions and Demands on Personal Time.	All these factors in the corresponding left column may have to be defined if chosen for use in the point rating method.

Source: Adapted from ICN (2010) & Palmer & Associates, Inc (n.d.)

After completion of factors' definition in step four, the JEC enters **STEP 5**. This step requires to determine the number of factor degrees that should be kept on the scale for each major factor and sub-factors if adopted for use in the process (Bergmann & Scarpello, 2001). The factor degrees also need to be defined for each factor to display the extent to which the compensable factor is present in the job as shown by examples in Table 2 on the Qualification compensable factor with 5-degree levels. It is advisable to have the same number of degrees for all job clusters to maintain consistency and usually the JEC may adopt four to six-factor degrees depending on members' judgment (Kaur, n.d.).

Table 2: Definition of Qualification Compensable factor Degrees Adopted for Use in Point Rating Method

Factor	1 st Degree	2 nd Degree	3 rd Degree	4 th Degree	5 th Degree
Qualification	-Basic education (high school or equivalent). No additional experience is required. -Basic language mathematics and technical or vocational trades' skills required in the job -No supervisory skills required.	-Basic education (high school) plus at least one year of relevant practical experience or equivalent. -Demonstrated proficiency in applying basic language, mathematics and technical/vocational trade skills required in the job -No supervisory skills required	-Mastery of basic paraprofessional or pre-bachelor's level language, mathematics and technical/vocational trades skills normally acquired through 2 years college or post-secondary technical/vocational training plus 0 to 4 years of relevant experiences OR -High school plus 2 to 4 years' experience required in the job	-Mastery of broad base of knowledge, technical, language and mathematical skills normally acquired through a bachelor degree curriculum plus 0 to 2 years relevant experience, OR -Two years of college plus 2 to 4 years of experience OR -High school plus 4 to 7 years experience	-Mastery of specialized knowledge and skills normally acquired through a master degree curriculum plus 0 to 2 years' experience OR -Bachelor's plus 2 to 4 years experience OR -Two years of college plus 4 to 7 years experience, OR -High school plus 7 to 10 years experience

Source: Adapted from Palmer & Associated, Inc (n.d)

Accomplishment of step five leads to **STEP 6** which involves the determination of total points plan to use in job evaluation (Bergmann & Scarpello, 2001). The JEC should have sufficient points to use in job evaluation but in most cases, the previous practices have included total points of 500 or 1000 points as suggested by many preceding scholars above. After determining the total points the JEC turns to weight the compensable factors in which the highest-ranking

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factor in the job will be assigned 100% weights and then the next highest factor will be assigned a value as a percentage of its importance to the first factor and so on (Dessler, 2001). The weights assigned to the compensable factors in this stage estimate the extent to which the factors are present in the job. An example of assigning weights to compensable factors of the Executive cluster of jobs may read as follows:

- Financial and Human Resources Management Responsibility 100% (given this percentage because it ranks highest in the management cluster jobs)
- Decision Making 95%
- Problem Solving 85%
- Knowledge 65%
- Physical Effort 50%

Next to assignment of weights, the JEC should sum-up the total percentage weights above and that summation can read as (100 + 95 + 85+ 65 + 50 = 395) (Dessler, 2001). Then the 395 value should be converted to 100% system as follows:

- Financial and Human Resources Management Responsibility $100 \div 395 = 25.32 = 25.3\%$
- Decision Making $95 \div 395 = 24.05 = 24.0\%$
- Problem Solving $85 \div 395 = 21.52 = 21.5\%$
- Knowledge $65 \div 395 = 16.46 = 16.5\%$
- Physical Effort $50 \div 395 = 12.66 = 12.7\%$

Totals = 100%

After determination of the total points and determining weights for each factor or sub-factors, the Job Evaluation Committee enters **STEP 7** which involves Assigning Point Values to Factors' Degrees (APVFD) (Bergmann & Scarpello, 2001; Dessler, 2001). In step 6 the total points and weights of factors were developed in percentages and therefore this step requires the JEC to allocate points to each compensable factor's degree as shown in Table 3 below. If the JEC decided to use a total of 1000 points plan, the financial and human resources responsibility factor weighted 25.3% will be allocated a total of $25.3\% \times 1000 = 253$ points.

So the JEC has resolved to allocate 253 points to financial and human resource management responsibility factors. This also means that the highest degree in the financial and human resource management factor will be assigned a total of 253 points. Then, points will be assigned to other degrees for the respective factor in equal amounts from lowest to highest degree. In this case, 253 points would be divided by the number of degrees (say, 5); and that will be 50.6 points for the lowest degree. The second degree in the similar factor will receive 101.2 points; plus 50.6 for 3rd degree = 151.8 points; plus 50.6 for 4th degree = 202.4; plus 50.6 for 5th degree = 253 points. The JEC will do this for every factor selected as shown in Table 3 below.

Table 3: Points Assigned to Factors and Degrees

Compensable Factors	1st Degree	2nd Degree	3rd Degree	4th Degree	5th Degree
Financial and Human Resource Management Responsibility	50.6	101.2	151.8	202.4	253
Decision Making	48	96	144	192	240
Problem Solving	43	86	129	172	215
Knowledge	33	66	99	132	165
Physical Effort	25.4	50.8	76.2	101.6	127
TOTALS	200	400	600	800	1000

Source: Author, 2021

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In case the organization's JEC opted to use the compensable factor and sub-factors, the weight in percentage for each factor will be divided by sub-factors depending on judgment to which each sub-factor exists in the job. Then, the JEC will calculate points for each sub-factor degree as shown in Table 4 below.

Table 4: Assigned Points to Compensable Sub-factors and their Degrees (If used in Job Evaluation)

Compensable Factors and Sub-factors	Factor Weight in %	1 st Degree	2 nd Degree	3 rd Degree	4 th Degree	5 th Degree
Financial and Human Resource Responsibility	25.3					
<i>Financial responsibilities</i>	12.8	25.6	51.2	76.8	102.4	128
<i>Human resource responsibilities</i>	12.5	25	50	75	100	125
Decision Making	24.0					
Non-routine decision making	14	28	56	84	112	140
Routine decision making	10	20	40	60	80	100
Problem Solving	21.5					
<i>Business Problem Solving</i>	8	16	32	48	64	80
<i>Inter-human Problem Solving</i>	7	14	28	42	56	70
<i>Intrapersonal Problem Solving</i>	6.5	13	26	39	52	65
Knowledge	16.5					
<i>Experience</i>	6.5	13	26	39	52	65
<i>Education</i>	6	12	24	36	48	60
<i>Job Skills</i>	4	8	16	24	32	40
Physical Effort	12.7					
Workload	8	16	32	48	64	80
Noise	3	6	12	18	24	30
Heat	1.7	3.4	6.8	10.2	13.6	17
TOTALS	100	100	200	400	600	800

Source: Author, 2021

After completion of step 7 above, the Job Evaluation Committee proceeds with **STEP 8** which becomes a preparation of the Job Evaluation Points Manual by establishing all points for factors and degrees for all clusters of jobs to be evaluated (Dessler, 2001). The Job Evaluation Points Manual in this case consolidates points of the Executive cluster of jobs as developed in step 7. The JEC will have to prepare the points manual for the rest of job clusters such as the Professional, Technical, Support and Manual job clusters as they proceed to establish points for those clusters.

Completion of the Job Evaluation Points Manual leads to the final 9th step of point rating (Bergmann & Scarpello, 2001). In step 9, the JEC rate the jobs as an actual evaluation (Kilgour, 2008). JEC uses the manual to rate various jobs as enlisted in different clusters (EOC, 2009). They rate the factors by drawing points from the factor degrees to which the factor exists in the job. Then, they sum up all the points and those jobs which score the highest points are considered the highest valuable jobs than the less scored job (Burke, 2008).

The JEC can also assign monetary values in terms of an hourly rate, daily rate, weekly rate whereby the highest points receive more monetary values (Kaur, n.d.). This action allows the JEC to determine the monthly salary of each job based on its points values and the corresponding monetary value for each point in the job cluster. When point rating is completed for all clusters of jobs, the JEC conducts the market pay survey to compare or adjust their decisions to achieve external comparability in pay rates of the organization. In addition, some Job Evaluation Committee may go extra miles by preparing job grades based on points and their likely pay structure (O'Riordan, 2008). The fulfillment of procedures above means that the point rating method has been implemented appropriately by the JEC.

3. PRACTICAL CASE OF POINT RATING FOR TRADES SKILLED JOBS AT A HYPOTHETICAL GENERAL PRINTERS' COMPANY LIMITED

This paper builds a hypothetical case of General Printers' Company Limited in which the owner wanted to conduct job evaluation. The jobs to be evaluated at the Company included the General Manager, Plant Supervisor, Accountant, Plant Marketer, Driver, Printer Machine Operator, Binder, Designer, Packer, Plant Stationer, and Assembler. The owner of the Company sought to conduct job evaluation to determine the worth of jobs as a base to implement equal pay for jobs of equal value. However, the owner of the Company realized that all personnel at the Company including himself did not have skills that could be used to evaluate the jobs by using the point rating method. He decided to invite the consultant at the Company premise to facilitate job evaluation undertaking using the point rating method under certain service contract.

Based on the previous section of this paper, when the consultant arrived at the Company to facilitate job evaluation, he began with some efforts of composing the Job Evaluation Committee as suggested by Mahmud (2019). The Job Evaluation Committee formulated by the consultant together with the Company owners consisted of four members including the Company owner, one employee representative, a representative from processing industries' trade union and the consultant who facilitated all processes of job evaluation.

After completion of Job Evaluation Committee composition and a short training for members, the consultant started step one of job evaluation. In this stage, the expert led a discussion among the Committee members on selecting the cluster of jobs to be evaluated. The owner of the Company presented at least three job clusters in which the first cluster consisted of the Trades Skilled jobs which comprised of the Printer Machine Operator, Binder, Designer, Packer, Plant Stationer, Driver, and Assembler. The second job cluster identified by the owner during their discussion was the Professional or Technical job cluster which included the Accountant and the Marketing Officer while the third cluster consisted of Management job which comprised the General Manager and the Plant Supervisor. Eventually, the Committee under the facilitation by the consultant decided to start job evaluation of the trades skilled job cluster because it had the majority of jobs compared to other clusters at the Company. They have planned to complete point rating for the respective cluster of jobs and then turn on other clusters of jobs later.

After selection of the Trades Skilled job cluster, the consultant informed the members of the Committee to undertake job analysis of all the jobs as required in step two. Fortunately, the owner of the Company had conducted a job analysis of all jobs in the respective job cluster. Members of the Committee resolved to use the available job description and specifications for the Printer Machines Operator, Binder, Designer, Packer, Plant Stationer, Driver, and Assembler jobs. Job analysis of all these jobs in the cluster would provide the first-hand job-related information on compensable factors that would be used to make decisions about the worth of jobs and their associated compensation components (Prachi, 2015).

Job analysis accomplishment in the second step above was followed by a selection of compensable factors (the job evaluation factors) as step three of job evaluation. The Committee decided to use a set of the compensable factors which they thought were relevant for Trades Skilled jobs. In this example, the paper assumes that the Job Evaluation Committee made a consensus and chose several major factors and their sub-factors in conducting point rating. The first compensable factors as chosen included Knowledge with sub-factors like education and training, experience and skills. The second was the Physical Working Conditions with its sub-factors of noise, temperature, physical efforts demands, and workloads (Tynes *et al.*, 2017). The third factor chosen was Quality of goods with sub-factors such as durable printouts, aesthetic printed material and reliable printouts as dimensions of quality (Sebastianelli & Tamimi, 2002). The fourth was the Mental Effort with sub-factors such as perceptual processing, verbal processing, and response processing while the fifth was the Work Complexity including mechanized networks, difficulty and multi-tasking as relevant sub-factors of work complexity (Shranz, 2018; Trujillo, 2019).

The step above was followed by step four in which the Committee decided to define each of the selected Compensable factors as suggested in previous major steps on point rating. In this Company case, the Committee briefly defined the major compensable factors including Knowledge, Physical Working Conditions, Quality of Goods, Mental Efforts, and Complexity of Work as displayed in Table 5 below. Definition of the compensable factors took place in this step because the Committee wanted to make them clear and comprehended by the Committee members.

Table 5: Brief Compensable Factors Definitions at General Printers’ Company Limited

Compensable Factors for Trades Skilled Jobs	Established Definitions by Job Evaluation Committee
Knowledge	Cognitive and psychomotor abilities acquired from informal and formal education and training. The factor includes sub-factors such as education and training, experience, and skills.
Physical Working Conditions	All physical environments that surround the jobs. The factor has sub-factors such as noise, temperature, physical efforts demands, and workloads
Quality of Goods	Efforts in ensuring that the printout at the Company conforms to quality standards. The factor is further divided into sub-factors like durable printouts, clean printouts, and aesthetic printed material
Mental Efforts	Brain information processing. The factor has sub-factors such as perceptual processing, verbal processing, and response processing
Complexity of Work	Complicated job in terms of its constituent elements. The factor has sub-factors such as mechanized networks, multi-tasking, and difficulty dimension experienced during job performance at the General Printers’ Company

Source: Author, 2021

Soon after completion of factor definition in step four above, the Committee at General Printers’ Company Limited turned to a decision about the necessary factor degrees to opt for use in the job evaluation project. The factor degree displays the extent to which compensable factors exist in the job during point rating (Kilgour, 2008). This actually was step five of the point rating method. In this example at General Printers’ Company Limited, five factors degree levels were decided for use in job evaluation. The consensus among members on factor degrees led to the task of defining each of the factor degrees. For brevity purposes, the paper presents a definition of degrees on the Physical Working Conditions as defined by the Committee members and illustrated in Table 6 below.

Table 6: Physical Working Conditions Degree Levels Definitions

Note: Consider the surrounding in which the individual works and the hazards to which he/she is exposed, such as poor lighting, heating, ventilation, high noise levels, infectious diseases, toxic chemicals, hazardous equipment, high working places, unpleasant weather, poor driving condition and so on.

Factor Degrees	Definition
1 st Degree	Normal office conditions prevail
2 nd Degree	Minimum exposure to unpleasant or hazardous conditions
3 rd Degree	Moderate exposure to unpleasant or hazardous conditions
4 th Degree	Above moderate exposure to unpleasant or hazardous conditions
5 th Degree	Maximum exposure to unpleasant conditions or hazardous conditions

Adapted from Palmer & Associate Inc, (n.d)

When the Committee had completed defining all the factor degrees in step five, they turned on decisions about the total points plan and weights for each factor in step six. The paper assumes that Committee at the Company decided a 500 to be used as the total points plan in the job evaluation project instead of 1000 points used in the second section of this paper. Therefore, the consensus about the total point plan led the members to another important sub-step of establishing the factor weights and distributes the weights of each factor to their sub-factors. The factor weights signified the extent to which the compensable factors existed in the job. In examples at General Printers’ Company Limited, the major factor weights as decided by the evaluaters were as follows:

- Quality of Goods 100%
- Mental Efforts 90%
- Physical Working Conditions 85%
- The complexity of Work 65%
- Knowledge 50%

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Based on our procedure in the previous section as suggested by Dessler (2001), the Committee members summed-up all the above percentages in the manner as: $(100+90+85+65+50 = 390)$. Then, 390 was converted into a 100% system as it was shown in section two of this paper. In our case, the General Printers’ Company Committee did the following computation on the factor weights.

- Quality of Goods $100 \div 390 = 25.64 = 26\%$
- Mental Effort $85 \div 390 = 21.79 = 22\%$
- Physical Working Conditions $75 \div 390 = 19.23 = 19\%$
- The complexity of Work $70 \div 390 = 17.94 = 18\%$
- Knowledge $60 \div 390 = 15.38 = 15\%$

Total = 100%

Then the Committee members distributed the factor weights to every sub-factor based on their judgment on the type of sub-factor which should receive more weight than others. An example of factor weights for Quality of Goods and its sub-factors at General Printers’ Company is calculated below while Table 7 displays the factor weights distribution for all major factors and associated sub-factors.

- Major factor = Quality of Goods with 26% weights. Then this is distributed to sub-factors based on judgment as indicated in the next three bullets:
- Durable Printouts 16%
- Clean Printouts 5%
- Aesthetic printed material 5%
- **Total = 26% weights**

Now in step 7, the Job Evaluation Committee under the facilitation of the consultant assigned point values to each compensable factor and their degrees based on step six. If the Committee assigned point values to the Quality of Goods sub-factors and associated degrees, the calculations were done as shown below for points in the fifth-degree level. Points scored in the 5th degree was divided by the number of degree levels to obtain the lowest point values in the 1st degree of which its values can be multiplied by degree levels to obtain the values for the 2nd, 3rd, 4th, and the 5th degree levels

- Quality of Goods 26%. (Major factor weights). Then distribute 26 % to sub-factors based on judgment as indicated in the next three bullets below.
- Durable Printouts $16 = 0.16 \times 500 \text{ points} = 80 \text{ points}$ for 5th factor degree
- Clean Printouts $5 = 0.05 \times 500 \text{ points} = 25 \text{ points}$ for 5th factor degree
- Aesthetic printed material $5 = 0.05 \times 500 = 25 \text{ points}$ for 5th factor degree

Table 7 summarizes the way Committee members assigned point values to each sub-factor and associated degrees. Point values assigned to every factor degree constitutes reference information when they begin point rating of various jobs in the Trades Skilled jobs cluster.

Table 7: Assigned Factor Degrees and Points Values to Sub-Factors at General Printers’ Company

Compensable Factors & Sub-factors	Factor Weight in %	1 st Degree	2 nd Degree	3 rd Degree	4 th Degree	5 th Degree
Quality of Goods	26					
Durable Printout	16	16	32	48	64	80
Clean Printouts	5	5	10	15	20	25
Aesthetic printed material	5	5	10	15	20	25

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Mental Effort	22						
Perceptual processing	9	9	18	27	36	45	
Verbal processing	7	7	14	21	28	35	
Response processing	6	6	12	18	24	30	
Physical Working Conditions	19						
Noise Level	6	6	12	18	24	30	
Temperature	5	5	10	15	20	25	
Physical effort demands	4	4	8	12	16	20	
Workload	4	4	8	12	16	20	
Complexity of Work	18						
Mechanized networks	9	9	18	27	36	45	
Multi-tasking	5	5	10	15	20	25	
Difficulty	4	4	8	12	16	20	
Knowledge	15						
Skills	7	7	14	21	28	35	
Education & Training	5	5	10	15	20	25	
Experience	3	3	6	9	12	15	
Total	100	100	100	200	300	400	500

Source: Author, 2021

When step 7 above was completed, the Committee members under the facilitation of the consultant prepared the Job Evaluation Points Manual by consolidating all the points of each factor and their degrees to be used as step eight of point rating method. The manual with points like those in Table 7 above was a guide for assigning points to jobs in the Trades Skilled jobs cluster. The Committee continued to establish points for other job clusters and prepared their points manual.

With completion of the Points Manual preparation as suggested in section two of this paper, the Committee began to use the point values in Table 7 to rate the points for all factors and degrees in the Trades Skilled job cluster as step nine. All points scored by every job were summed-up and the job with the highest points became the most worthy job relative to others. Table 8 below displays that the Printer Machine Operator scored the highest points (308) and therefore was the most worthy job at the Company’s job hierarchy. The job also would receive high pay in decisions related to pay.

The second worthy job in this example was the Assembler which scored (255 points), followed by the Plant Stationer (222 points), Binder (163 points), Designer (136 points), Driver (136 points), and Packer (100 points). The JEC members proceeded with the same procedures to develop points for other jobs clusters identified at the Company.

Table 8: Points Scored by Trades Skilled Jobs at a Hypothetical General Printers’ Company

S/No	Jobs	Total Points out of (500)
1	Printer Machine Operator	308
2.	Assembler	255
3.	Plant Stationer	222
4.	Binder	163
5.	Designer	138
6.	Driver	136
7.	Packer	100

Source: Author, 2021

4. CONCLUSION

This paper believes that a clear understanding of point rating method procedures as elaborated above is a necessary pre-condition for using this technique correctly to reach robust results. The current fragmented sources of information about point rating analytical technique is a barrier for effective participation in job evaluation by many evaluators. Most job

evaluators such as managers, employee representatives, interns and trade unions' representatives lack the skills and information when appointed to join the Job Evaluation Committee in the workplaces. The paper has practically applied the point rating method procedures to attempt to rate the points to the Trades Skilled jobs using the anticipated procedures that might have been used by the Job Evaluation Committee at the General Printers' Company Limited. This has been done to extend knowledge and skills acquisition among stakeholders of job evaluation. The paper has no doubt that its perusal by employees, managers, interns and unions' representative will enhance their ability to participate actively in point rating when evaluating the organization's jobs

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